

SOME PROPERTIES OF THE EULER QUOTIENT MATRIX

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Abstract

Let a and m be integers such that $(a, m) = 1$. Let $q_a = \frac{a^{\phi(m)} - 1}{m}$. We call q_a the Euler Quotient of m with base a . This is called the Fermat Quotient when m is a prime. We consider some properties of the matrix of Euler Quotients reduced modulo m and show that these quotients are uniformly distributed modulo m .

1. Introduction

Let m and a be integers such that $(m, a) = 1$. Let $q_a = \frac{a^{\phi(m)} - 1}{m}$. We call q_a the Euler Quotient of m with base a . This is called the Fermat Quotient when m is a prime.

The following theorem summarizes some of the logarithmic properties of q_a .

Theorem 1.1 Let $a, b \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $r \in \mathbb{N}$ with $(a, m) = (b, m) = 1$. Then

- (a) $q_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{m}$
- (b) $q_{ab} \equiv q_a + q_b \pmod{m}$
- (c) $q_{a^r} \equiv r q_a \pmod{m}$

Additional properties of q_a are given by the following generalization of a theorem of Wells [4]. It provides conditions when q_a vanishes modulo m .

Theorem 1.2 Let $(a, m) = 1$. If l and t are integers with $(l, m) = 1$ and α is a positive integer, then for $a = l + tm^\alpha$

$$q_a \equiv q_l \pmod{m + \frac{\phi(m)t}{l} m^{\alpha-1} \pmod{m^\alpha}}.$$

2. The Euler Quotient Matrix

Let a be the i^{th} integer such that $1 \leq a \leq m$ and $(a, m) = 1$. The Euler Quotient Matrix, M_m , is the $m \times \phi(m)$ matrix where the entries in column i are the least non-negative residues of $q_k \pmod{m}$ for $k \leq m^2$ and $k \equiv a \pmod{m}$. To be more precise we may call this the order 2 matrix and define the order r matrix for $k \leq m^r$, $r = 1, 2, \dots$, to be the $m^{r-1} \times \phi(m)$ matrix M_{m^r} .

Example 2.1 The Euler Quotient Matrices for $m = 7, 12$ and 9 are given below.

a=	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	0	2	6	4	6	1
2	6	5	1	2	3	2
3	5	1	3	0	0	3
4	4	4	5	5	4	4
5	3	0	0	3	1	5
6	2	3	2	1	5	6
7	1	6	4	6	2	0

a=	1	5	7	11
1	0	4	8	8
2	4	0	0	4
3	8	8	4	0
4	0	4	8	8
5	4	0	0	4
6	8	8	4	0
7	0	4	8	8
8	4	0	0	4
9	8	8	4	0
10	0	4	8	8
11	4	0	0	4
12	8	8	4	0

a=	1	2	4	5	7	8
1	0	7	5	8	4	3
2	6	1	2	2	1	6
3	3	4	8	5	7	0
4	0	7	5	8	4	3
5	6	1	2	2	1	6
6	3	4	8	5	7	0
7	0	7	5	8	4	3
8	6	1	2	2	1	6
9	3	4	8	5	7	0

Definition 2.2 Let π_i be the maximum size of the blocks of non-repeated entries in the i^{th} column. We call π_i the period of column i .

Theorem 2.3 The period of column i is given by $\pi_i = \frac{m}{(\phi(m), m)}$ for all $i \leq \phi(m)$.

Proof. Suppose column i contains the least non-negative residue of $q_a \pmod{m}$ such that $a \equiv l + tm$, $l < m$ and $(l, m) = 1$. Then by Theorem 1.2, taking $\alpha = 1$, we have $q_a \equiv q_l + \phi(m)tl^{-1} \pmod{m}$. The residues of q_a and q_l are equal precisely when m divides $\phi(m)t$. This occurs for the first time when $t = \frac{m}{(\phi(m), m)}$ and subsequently for every integer multiple of t . Thus period of column i , $\pi_i = \frac{m}{(\phi(m), m)}$.

Definition 2.4 We define the period of M_m to be the period of each column. That is, period of M_m is given by $\pi_m = \frac{m}{(\phi(m), m)}$.

Let $A_r^m = \{q_a \pmod{m} : 0 \leq a < m^r\}$. It is of interest to know the size of A_r^m . We list some properties of A_r^m .

- (a) When $m = p$, a prime and $r = 1$, Vandiver [5] showed that $\sqrt{p} \leq |A_1^p| \leq p - (1 + \sqrt{2p - 5})/2$.
- (b) When $r = 2$ and m is a prime or a strong pseudoprime $|A_2^m| = m$.

- (c) I don't know of any bounds apart from the trivial bounds for $|A_1^m|$ when m is not prime.
- (d) Let m be an integer with $m > 2$. Then we have that

$$\frac{m}{(m, \phi(m))} \leq |A_2^m| \leq \frac{m}{(m, \phi(m))} \frac{\phi(m)}{2}.$$

We note that these bounds are the best possible. For example, when m is a prime, $m = 4$, or $m = 12$, the lower bound is achieved. When $m = 3^\alpha, \alpha \geq 2$, the upper bound is achieved.

In fact we have

$$\frac{m}{(m, \phi(m))} \leq |A_r^m| \leq \frac{m}{(m, \phi(m))} \frac{\phi(m)}{2}$$

whenever $r \geq 2$.

Another area of interest is the vanishing of the quotients modulo m .

The following theorem appearing in [1] characterizes the elements of M_m and gives a formula for the number of vanishing quotients modulo m in M_m .

Theorem 2.5 Let $m = p^{\alpha_1} \dots p^{\alpha_k}$ be the prime factorization of the integer $m \geq 2$ and q the homomorphism from $(\mathbb{Z}/m^2\mathbb{Z})^\times$ into $(\mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z}, +)$ induced by the Euler quotient of m . For $1 \leq r \leq k$ put $m_r = p^{\alpha_r}$ and

$$d_r = \begin{cases} (m_r, 2 \prod_{j=1}^k (p_j - 1)), & \text{when } m_r = 2^{\alpha_r}; \alpha_r \geq 2, \\ (m_r, \prod_{j=1}^k (p_j - 1)), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let $d = \prod_{r=1}^k d_r$. Then the image $q((\mathbb{Z}/m^2\mathbb{Z})^\times)$ equals $\{td + m\mathbb{Z} : 0 \leq t \leq (m/d) - 1\}$; it is therefore isomorphic to $(\mathbb{Z}/(m/d)\mathbb{Z}, +)$ for $m > 2$.

The above theorem immediately leads to the fact that the number of quotients to vanish modulo m in M_m is $d\phi(m)$. A quick glance at the matrices for $m = 7, 12$ and 9 shows that a matrix may have columns containing no vanishing quotients. Using the period of the Euler quotient matrix and the total number of zero entries we obtain the following.

Theorem 2.6 Let d be as defined in Theorem 2.5 and $m \geq 2$ be an integer. Then the number of columns of M_m containing zeros is given by $\frac{d\phi(m)}{(\phi(m), m)}$.

Proof. The proof is just to recognize that the number of zeros in each column with a zero is given by $\frac{m}{\pi_m} = (\phi(m), m)$. Now, by Theorem 2.5 the total number of zeros in M_m is $d\phi(m)$. Thus, there are exactly $\frac{d\phi(m)}{(\phi(m), m)}$ columns with a least one zero.

The formula for the number of columns without zeros is more interesting. This is given by $\phi(m)(1 - \frac{d}{(\phi(m), m)})$. If one notes that when m is a prime or a strong pseudoprime $d = (\phi(m), m) = 1$, then the term $\frac{d}{(\phi(m), m)}$ can be considered as measure of the primeness of m .

3. Sum of Quotients in the Columns and Rows of M_m

In the next two theorems we, respectively, show that the sum of the entries in each column of M_m is congruent to 0 modulo m and that all rows sum to the same constant modulo m .

Theorem 3.1 Let $1 \leq a < m$ with $(a, m) = 1$. If $k < m^2$ and $k \equiv a \pmod{m}$, then

$$\sum_{k \equiv a \pmod{m}} q_k \equiv 0 \pmod{m}.$$

Proof. Let $k = a + im, i < m$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k \equiv a \pmod{m}} q_k &= \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} (a + im)^{\phi(m)-1} = \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} q_a + \binom{\phi(m)}{1} \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} i a^{\phi(m)-1} + \\ &\quad m \left\{ \binom{\phi(m)}{2} \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} i^2 a^{\phi(m)-2} + \dots + \binom{\phi(m)}{\phi(m)} \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} i^{\phi(m)} a^{0} \right\} \\ &= m q_a + \phi(m) m (m-1) a^{\phi(m)-1} \equiv 0 \pmod{m} \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.2 $\sum_{\substack{a=km+1 \\ (a,m)=1}}^{(k+1)m-1} q_a \equiv \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,m)=1}}^{m-1} q_a \pmod{m}$, for each $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, m-1\}$.

Proof. For any $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, m-1\}$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{\substack{a=km+1 \\ (a,m)=1}}^{(k+1)m-1} q_a &= \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ (a,m)=1}}^{m-1} \frac{(km+a)^{\phi(m)} - 1}{m} \\ &= \dagger \frac{1}{m} \left\{ \phi(m) m^{\phi(m)} + \binom{\phi(m)}{1} \sum_{\substack{a < m \\ (a,m)=1}} m^{\phi(m)-1} a + \binom{\phi(m)}{2} \sum_{\substack{a < m \\ (a,m)=1}} m^{\phi(m)-2} a^2 + \dots + \right. \\ &\quad \left. \binom{\phi(m)}{\phi(m)-1} \sum_{\substack{a < m \\ (a,m)=1}} m a^{\phi(m)-1} + \sum_{\substack{a < m \\ (a,m)=1}} (a^{\phi(m)} - 1) \right\} \\ &= \phi(m) m^{\phi(m)-1} + m^{\phi(m)-2} \binom{\phi(m)}{1} \sum_{\substack{a < m \\ (a,m)=1}} a + m^{\phi(m)-3} \binom{\phi(m)}{2} \sum_{\substack{a < m \\ (a,m)=1}} a^2 + \dots + \\ &\quad \phi(m) \sum_{\substack{a < m \\ (a,m)=1}} a^{\phi(m)-1} + \sum_{\substack{a < m \\ (a,m)=1}} q_a \\ &\equiv \sum_{\substack{a < m \\ (a,m)=1}} q_a \pmod{m}. \end{aligned}$$

[†] From this point on we suppressed, without loss, the use of k in the proof.

4. Equidistribution of the Euler Quotients

A result due to Heath-Brown [3] shows that the Fermat Quotients are uniformly distributed mod p for $1 \leq a < p$. This result generalized nicely to the Euler Quotients. We obtain

Theorem 4.1 For any integers a, h with $(a, m) = (h, m) = 1$, we have

$$\sum_{\substack{M < a < M+N \\ (a,m)=1}} \exp\left(\frac{hq_a}{m}\right) \ll N^{1/2}m^{3/8} \text{ uniformly for } M, N \geq 1.$$

In particular

$$\sum_{\substack{a < m \\ (a,m)=1}} \exp\left(\frac{hq_a}{m}\right) \ll m^{7/8} \text{ uniformly.}$$

Proof. The proof is similar to that of Heath-Brown [3]. From Theorem 1.1 we have $q_{ab} \equiv q_a + q_b \pmod{m}$ whenever $(a, m) = (b, m) = 1$. Thus

$$\chi(a) = \begin{cases} 0, & (a, m) \neq 1 \\ \exp\left(\frac{hq_a}{m}\right), & (a, m) = 1. \end{cases}$$

is a non-principal character of order m . Hence we have

$$\sum_{M < a < M+N} \exp\left(\frac{hq_a}{m}\right) = \sum_{M < a < M+N} \chi(a).$$

Now Burgess [2] proved that for composite modulus m

$$\sum_{M < a < M+N} \chi(a) \ll N^{1/2}m^{3/8}.$$

Taking $M = 1$ and $N = m$, we obtain

$$\sum_{\substack{a < m \\ (a,m)=1}} \exp\left(\frac{hq_a}{m}\right) \ll m^{7/8}, \text{ uniformly.}$$

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